

1 **Policy documents considering climate, biodiversity and land use in the European Arctic**
2 **reveal visible, hidden and imagined nexus approaches**

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Summary

The Arctic is experiencing rapid and interlinked socio-environmental changes. Therefore, governance approaches which take the complex interactions between climate change, biodiversity loss, increasing land use pressures, and local livelihoods into account are needed; nexus approaches. However, an overview of whether and to what extent Arctic policies address these nexus elements in concert has been missing. We analyzed a large sample of publicly available assessment reports and policy documents from the terrestrial European Arctic. Our results show that although the nexus approaches are widely adopted in Arctic policy reporting, the emphasis varies among the governance levels, and documents underestimate certain interactions: local communities and traditional livelihoods are seldom seen as actors with agency and impact. Practical implementations were identified as potential advancements in the Arctic governance: ecosystem-specific, technological and authoritative solutions, co-production of knowledge, and adaptive co-management. Implementation of nexus approaches can promote more holistic environmental governance and guide cross-sectoral policies.

55 **Introduction**

56

57 The Arctic region is warming two to four times faster than any other region in the world¹,
58 putting stress on the environments and social-ecological systems (SES) adapted to cold
59 conditions and seasonality²⁻⁴. Higher temperatures, melting sea and land ice, together with
60 thawing permafrost and changing snow conditions, are transforming ecosystems, faster than
61 elsewhere on the planet. Interactions and dynamics between organisms change, with potential
62 knock-on effects across trophic levels⁵. Plants grow faster and taller, and at higher altitudes,
63 than one human generation ago⁶⁻⁸. Other Arctic biodiversity transitions⁹ include changes in
64 phenology (timing of leaf emergence, flowering/senescence of plants), vegetation
65 composition, and plant traits (e.g. leaf and stem characteristics), all of which contribute to the
66 overall functional diversity¹⁰⁻¹².

67

68 These changes in climate and biodiversity alter key ecosystem functions such as carbon
69 sequestration and sink/source dynamics of Arctic soils¹³, along with the potential release of
70 carbon dioxide and methane from thawing Arctic permafrost¹⁴. Boreal and temperate species
71 are projected to expand their ranges northward, thus potentially increasing overall species
72 richness, at the expense of endemic Arctic species¹⁵. Ongoing changes pose threats to local
73 livelihood activities, and, in so doing, may erode culturally unique human-environment
74 interactions, including many environmentally sustainable practices^{16,17}. Traditional
75 livelihoods (e.g. hunting, fishing, gathering, small-scale forestry and agriculture and herding
76 activities) in the Arctic are in close interaction with the environment and the land, and all
77 them remain important components of Arctic culture and tradition today¹⁸. They are being
78 shaped by the ongoing environmental changes, and, at the same time, local communities
79 continue to shape ecosystems through their livelihoods and cultural management practices.

80

81 Currently in the transition towards sustainable future, rich and diverse pool of natural
82 resources make the Arctic attractive for economic development and can turn some challenges
83 posed by climate change into opportunities – for some at least^{2,19}. Increased activity and
84 industrial development demands increasing the built area, such as road and rail infrastructure
85 for transportation, settlements for employees and infrastructure for power transmission
86 lines^{20,21}. Although the economic development in the Arctic brings opportunities to some, the
87 distribution of risks and costs of the long-term developments is not necessarily equal among
88 Arctic peoples²⁰. For example, infrastructure development and fragmentation decrease the
89 flexibility of reindeer herding practices in space and time, which has been identified as key to
90 reducing vulnerability of this traditional livelihood to climate change²²⁻²⁴.

91

92 Given their complex cultural and natural resource-based dependency on the local
93 environment, local communities practicing traditional livelihoods are highly susceptible to
94 climate change, biodiversity loss and intensifying land use. While the Arctic Peoples are used
95 to a dynamic environment and constant adaptation, the changes now are happening faster
96 than ever before in human history and are even accelerating^{25,26}. Understanding and
97 managing the effects of multiple simultaneous changes is especially critical in the Arctic,
98 where intertwined socio-environmental challenges impact landscapes and SESs. It is
99 increasingly recognized that due to their synergistic or amplifying effects, outcomes of the
100 before-mentioned processes may be unexpected, and their impacts are not only additive.
101 Solutions to current socio-environmental problems cannot be designed by focusing on single
102 challenges²⁷; instead, holistic approaches are needed^{28,29}.

103

104 We consider a nexus approach as a key for Arctic policies to cope with the intertwined socio-
105 environmental challenges. According to Wormbs and Sörlin (2017), “no other region of the
106 world has as many scientific assessments per capita as the Arctic”³⁰. However, so far, an
107 overview of whether Arctic assessments and policy documents address these nexus elements
108 in concert has not been presented. *A nexus* can be defined as a set of context-specific critical
109 interlinkages between two or more elements³¹. The nexus approach provides an integrated
110 framework for addressing multiple sectors or drivers simultaneously. In so doing,
111 implementation of nexus approaches can guide cross-sectoral policies and promote more
112 holistic environmental governance and policy coherence³¹⁻³³. Over the past decade, academic
113 interest in the nexus approach has rapidly increased, especially in research that focuses on
114 complex socio-environmental challenges³⁴⁻³⁶.

115

116 Here, we analyzed a large sample of publicly available assessment reports and policy
117 documents from a sub-region of European Arctic, and across international, European Union,
118 regional, national, and subnational governance levels. We concentrate on two research
119 questions: 1) to what extent these documents address two or more of the Arctic policy
120 elements together, and 2) what kind of approaches these documents propose for future
121 implementation and advancement of nexus-based policies in the Arctic. Our results indicate
122 that across all levels, there is variation in how often the four dimensions of the climate
123 change – biodiversity – land use – local community nexus are considered as drivers of
124 change, as opposed to something being impacted. Most of the analysed documents considered
125 the “full nexus”, in the sense of acknowledging interlinkages between at least three nexus
126 elements simultaneously. Approximately half of the national and subnational level documents
127 studied did not consider the full nexus. We consider knowledge gaps and policy
128 recommendations listed in the documents to represent narratives about possible and desirable

129 futures³⁷. Knowledge gaps and policy recommendations implying nexus approach
130 demonstrate how Arctic policy is imagined to govern interlinking nexus elements in the
131 future.

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133

134 **Results**

135

136 **Methods summary**

137

138 Policies addressing the Arctic nexus elements together are supporting each other in the
139 overall aim of addressing climate change, biodiversity loss, land use, and local community
140 development as intertwined elements of the same system; they promote the Arctic policy
141 coherence³³. Policy coherence has two dimensions: *outputs* (including policy objectives as
142 well as policy design and instruments for achieving them) and *implementation* practices at
143 different levels³⁸. We study the output dimension by analyzing how assessment reports and
144 policy documents, considered as key outputs, address the nexus elements together. The
145 implementation dimension is addressed by analyzing the policy recommendations and
146 knowledge gaps put forward in the documents. In order to examine whether policies address
147 nexus elements together, we applied document analysis³⁹ combined with qualitative and
148 semi-quantitative content analysis⁴⁰, on a total of 80 documents, of which 15 were
149 international, 13 European Union (EU) -level, 9 regional (Nordic, Barents, Sápmi), 28
150 national and 15 subnational (see the Experimental procedures and Note S1 for details).

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153

154 **Visible nexus in the Arctic policy documents**

155

156 The majority (76 out of 80) of the documents analyzed acknowledged a connection or
157 connections linking climate change, biodiversity, land use change, and/or local communities
158 together (material list found in Note S1). We did not identify recognition of linkages between
159 any nexus elements in AMAP (Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme, 2018;
160 international level), EC (European Commission 2020a; EU level), Lundgren et al. (2020;
161 regional level) or Nordregion Secretariat (2021; regional level; see Note S1 for details). Our
162 analysis captured nexus approaches in all of the national and subnational governance level
163 reports.

164

165 Although the Arctic policy nexus was visible in most of the documents, our results suggest
166 that some dimensions of the climate – biodiversity – land use – local community nexus were
167 more commonly recognized than others (Figure 2, Table S1). Moreover, we detected
168 differences regarding which dimension(s) of the nexus the five governance levels focused on.
169 At the international level, the interactions between all nexus elements were acknowledged
170 rather uniformly (Figure 2: relatively equal connections between the four elements), whereas
171 the other spatial scales had stronger emphasis on specific dimensions (Figure 2: variation in
172 the strength of the connections). For instance, in comparison to the other dimensions of the
173 nexus, many EU-level reports acknowledged the interrelated nature of climate change and
174 land use. At the regional level, in turn, land use – local community interdependencies were
175 recognized by most reports. Further, at the subnational level the land use – local community –
176 biodiversity interactions were acknowledged by more reports than their interactions with
177 climate change. Similarly, there were dimensions in the nexus that were less recognized than
178 others: interdependencies between local communities and biodiversity at the national level,

179 between biodiversity and climate change at the regional level, and between local
180 communities and land use at the EU-level.
181
182 Moreover, while the nexus approach emphasizes the interdependencies between the different
183 nexus elements, our findings suggest variation in how often the four dimensions of the
184 climate change – biodiversity – land use – local community nexus were considered as drivers,
185 as opposed to something being impacted. The results indicate that across all levels, the
186 reports commonly discuss biodiversity as impacted by climate change, land use change and
187 local livelihoods (Figure 2: small biodiversity node sizes in comparison to other node sizes),
188 rather than as a driver for climate change (e.g. buffering climate change impacts) or local
189 communities (e.g. limiting customary practices). This finding is also evidenced by a notable
190 variation between the governance levels in acknowledging the agency of local communities
191 in influencing biodiversity, climate change and land use change (see differences in local
192 community -node sizes in Figure 2). For example, only a minority of the EU-level reports
193 analyzed discussed biodiversity – local community interactions, and we detected no
194 acknowledgement of the influence of local communities on land use. Our results at the EU-
195 level suggest, in fact, that in comparison to the other dimensions of the climate change –
196 biodiversity - land use – local community nexus, local communities were most rarely
197 identified as drivers of change in comparison to the other nexus elements. On the contrary,
198 the land use – local community interactions were acknowledged in most of the regional-level
199 reports, as well as in approximately half of the national and subnational level reports. At the
200 international level, the local communities’ influence, in particular on biodiversity, was well-
201 recognized. Similar governance-level differences can be detected in the frequency of reports
202 that position climate change and land use as a driver (Figure 2: climate change and land use -
203 node sizes).

204

205 Most of the documents analyzed considered the “full nexus”, in the sense of acknowledging
206 interlinkages between at least three nexus elements simultaneously. All except one of the
207 international level documents and all but one of the EU-level documents considered the full
208 nexus at least acknowledging that more than two elements interact; the same applies to
209 regional level documents (Barents, Nordic, Sápmi). In many of the assessment reports, the
210 biodiversity changes experienced in the Arctic ecosystems were considered to be driven by
211 multiple pressures such as climate-change driven permafrost degradation and growing
212 pressures from increased human presence (CAFF 2013, 2021). These pressures were
213 considered as having harmful feedbacks to local communities and Indigenous peoples,
214 because of their “dependence on the environment for food, lifestyle, and culture” (AMAP
215 2017). European Environment Agency (EEA 2017) explained the “integrated framework for
216 the risk of climate-related impacts” meaning that climate change, emissions and land-use
217 changes are linked, and they are linked to socio-economic processes, risks and vulnerabilities.
218 Half of the national-level documents studied did not consider the full nexus. Holistic
219 consideration of several topics was often outside the aim and scope of these documents. Also,
220 approximately half of the subnational level documents studied did not consider the full nexus.

221

222 **Ways forward by policy recommendations**

223

224 Of the 80 documents, 33 gave policy recommendations or suggested solutions related to
225 linkages between the nexus elements or full nexus (Table 1). Of the documents, 24 also listed
226 knowledge gaps, further research needs or areas for further thinking and deeper dive, related
227 to interlinkages between the nexus elements (Table 2).

228

229 We clustered the policy recommendations and knowledge gaps from Tables 1 and 2 into five
230 general categories. The first category is about *ecosystem-specific solutions* taking interlinked
231 nexus elements into consideration. The policy documents proposed ecosystem-specific (e.g.
232 wetlands; carbon rich ecosystems) solutions for protection and restoration of ecosystems in a
233 way that can mitigate climate change, and recognize land use impacts and concerns of local
234 communities. Furthermore, transboundary collaboration recognizing ecosystem boundaries in
235 addition to administrative ones was put forward. This could also help to mitigate
236 environmental hazards (e.g. floods; climate; droughts; soil erosion) across administrative
237 borders. Especially EU level policy documents highlighted the importance of setting policy
238 targets across scales to meet sustainability goals and respond to Indigenous Peoples’
239 concerns, tailoring policies to local and regional contexts, and enhancing cross-sectoral and
240 multi-level governance to address nexus issues.

241

242 The second category relates to *co-production of knowledge* among researchers and
243 Indigenous Peoples of intertwined nexus elements. For example, the policy documents
244 suggest future-oriented thinking on adaptation strategies and environmental change, and
245 bringing forward realities of Indigenous Peoples. In addition, mapping and monitoring
246 ecosystems and their change as assessed by research and collection of Indigenous Knowledge
247 was proposed as a method of combining the various nexus elements. Data and closing the
248 data gaps was often seen as a key to many policies, including emergency responses and
249 building resilience. The third category identified links to *technological solutions* for
250 developing renewable resource use, combining green and grey solutions for transformative
251 change, developing circular economy and smart solutions, and engaging companies in
252 designing and developing environmental solutions.

253

254 The fourth category links to *adaptive co-management* combining science, local knowledge
255 and local ecosystem management. Policy documents for example propose that impact
256 assessment processes should include scientific knowledge and the knowledge systems of
257 Indigenous Peoples', that multiple stressors on Arctic species and ecosystems should be
258 addressed by holistic interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches, and that a more
259 holistic approach could be supported by developing advisory services for agriculture. The
260 fifth category links to *authoritative solutions* with an aim of informing people about ongoing
261 changes and enforcing regulations also on local livelihoods such as reindeer herding.
262 Nevertheless, traditional livelihoods are seldom mentioned in the policy recommendations
263 and knowledge gaps listed, especially at the international and EU level.

264

265 **Discussion**

266

267 More holistic environmental governance in the Arctic requires nexus approaches; taking the
268 complex interactions between climate change, biodiversity loss, increasing land use
269 pressures, and local livelihoods into account. An overview of whether and to what extent
270 Arctic policies address these nexus elements in concert has been missing. The analysis
271 presented here paper helps to close this knowledge gap. Above we examined how assessment
272 reports and policy documents at multiple governance levels considered these nexus elements
273 together. The nexus approach provides a useful way of addressing multiple simultaneous
274 environmental and societal challenges. The approach has been explicitly applied in the Arctic
275 context for example by Chuffart et al.⁴¹ (EU-Arctic nexus and the Green Deal), and
276 Huntington et al.⁴² (Arctic food-water-energy nexus). The Sustainable Development Working
277 Group of the Arctic Council launched in 2020 the water, energy and food nexus study⁴³,
278 contributing to the attainment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals in the

279 Arctic (<https://www.arctic-council.org/news/nexus-between-water-energy-and-food-in-the->
280 arctic/). The nexus approach is especially timely in the Arctic region, where mutually
281 reinforcing twin crises of climate change and biodiversity loss, in concert with societal and
282 geopolitical changes, is projected to lead to irreversible changes to ecosystems and human
283 communities^{1,2,9,44}. Here we discuss two aspects of the nexus approach corresponding to
284 Nilsson et al.³⁸ dimensions under policy coherence: policy outputs, and policy
285 implementation. Our analysis provides insights on moving beyond policies addressing single
286 challenges towards more holistic approach, which also has potential to reduce conflicts and
287 promotes synergies between and within different policy areas³⁸. We emphasise that nexus
288 approach is a key for policies able to move towards sustainable Arctic of tomorrow.

289

290 **Nexus in policy outputs**

291

292 Prior research has criticized the nexus approach for not being able to move beyond its
293 buzzword status, or for remaining a mainly theoretical approach, and thus, integrated
294 approaches in sustainable development continue to be exception rather than rule²⁹. Examined
295 against the backdrop of such criticism, and the argument that the nexus approach is in its
296 infancy regarding its application and implementation, unexpectedly frequent and diverse
297 nexus approaches were visible in the Arctic policy documents and assessment reports. Focus
298 on integrated social-ecological systems may have contributed to frequent nexus approach in
299 the Arctic research^{45,46}. However, addressing nexus elements together in scientific papers or
300 by policy documents are very different issues, even though European Arctic may be
301 exemplary region in this sense, with local communities nesting within larger, wealthy
302 nations. On the other hand, the interlinkages between the nexus elements were acknowledged

303 to varying extents, at different governance scales. Approximately half of the national and
304 subnational level documents analyzed did not consider the “full nexus” – three or four nexus
305 elements together – even if the topic of the document indicated a holistic approach.

306

307 Local communities, as well as biodiversity, were often seen as something being affected, not
308 as actors with agency, or as active drivers of change. This has been noted also in earlier
309 research; it has been pointed out that Arctic assessment reports have limited view of
310 environmental and societal drivers³⁰, and the social and cultural complexity of the region is
311 often forgotten. In our view, to maximize their impact, biodiversity assessments should
312 increasingly incorporate a systemic view: they should consider complex feedbacks and
313 interactions between species and biogeophysical systems (including sub-surface), and human
314 activities – all as parts of manifold SES. In West Siberia and Northern Fennoscandia, for
315 example, Indigenous Sámi and Nenets reindeer herders have reported changes in height and/or
316 encroachment of woody plants, and related alterations in reindeer grazing regimes^{6,47,48}.
317 Permafrost degradation interacts with reindeer herding, as well⁴⁹. A growing body of evidence
318 suggests that traditional management practices of Indigenous Peoples or local communities’
319 ways of life can support conservation⁹ and be part of solutions towards climate change
320 mitigation. For example, grazing reduces vegetation height and shrub expansion through
321 browsing and trampling, which, in turn, may influence regional climate change through land-
322 atmosphere feedbacks⁵⁰⁻⁵².

323

324 At different governance levels, various categories of human activity or sectors of industrial
325 activity are seen as affecting the other nexus elements. Industrial/sectoral strategies were part
326 of our selection of research material, and at the international level these concentrated on oil
327 and gas production and industrial pollution, at the EU-level on forestry, agriculture and

328 energy sectors, and at the national and subnational levels on forestry and energy sectors as
329 well as reindeer herding. The selected regional strategy papers (from Nordic, Barents and
330 Sápmi regions) concentrated on reindeer herding and other traditional Sámi livelihoods.
331 Local Arctic communities have long used ecosystems (for example as rangelands) and their
332 relationship with the animals as sentient beings, and nature in general, has been central to
333 their worldview and well-being⁵³⁻⁵⁵. This view of strongly coupled human – non-human
334 interactions dovetails with part of the reports analyzed: land use, local communities and
335 biodiversity co-occurred in several reports at the subnational level, as well as land use and
336 biodiversity.

337

338 **Imagined nexus through ideas for policy implementation**

339

340 It is crucial to address not only whether and to what extent existing policy outputs consider
341 nexus elements together, but also to consider how these policy documents imagine the role of
342 policy innovations in endorsing Arctic SES by implementing new practices. We consider that
343 knowledge gaps and policy recommendations found in the documents analyzed represent
344 narratives about what kinds of futures are possible and desirable³⁷. These relate to the aspect
345 of policy implementation - arrangements to put policy plans into action³⁸. The knowledge
346 gaps and policy recommendations can offer key insights into how abstract nexus approaches
347 can be concretized. In practice, they demonstrate how Arctic policy is imagined to govern
348 interlinking nexus elements in the future, while operating within the principles of sustainable
349 environmental governance.

350

351 For instance, the category “ecosystem-specific solutions” aims for ecosystem-based
352 management⁵⁶ and to matching ecosystem and governance scales to avoid scale misfit of

353 environmental management^{57,58}. Another example is provided by the categories “co-
354 production of knowledge” and “adaptive co-management” which acknowledge the necessity
355 of co-production processes to engage Indigenous and local communities and also address
356 power relations and governance issues^{59,60}. In this context, reindeer herding gains importance
357 at pan-Arctic, regional, national and subnational level: reindeer are keystone herbivores in
358 circumpolar SESs. Humans and their semi-domesticated reindeer herds have been affecting
359 landscape-level tundra and taiga ecosystem dynamics for two millennia or longer⁶¹⁻⁶⁴. Co-
360 producing knowledge with herders - and understanding herding at least partly as
361 environmental stewardship - would be one way towards better climate change adaptation and
362 mitigation, and to avoid choosing policies that may have unintentional and unwanted local
363 and regional side effects.

364

365 The categories link to quite different ways of thinking about policy and sustainability. There
366 is no single type of solution to improve the nexus approach, but scientists, technology
367 developers, policy makers, and local communities can - and should - each have their role and
368 strengths in improving and implementing the nexus approach.

369

370 **Hidden nexus and other limitations of the study**

371

372 We found that nexus is occasionally tacitly considered in policy documents and assessment
373 reports. A key limitation in our methodology is its inability to identify the “hidden” nexuses
374 in documents, if they use integrative concepts or umbrella terms^{65,66} that cover the
375 interlinkages between the nexus elements without mentioning them explicitly. Several
376 concepts, functioning as umbrella terms and implicitly capturing the nexus approach, were
377 found in the documents analyzed: bioeconomy, circular economy, green transition, resilience,

378 one health, sustainability and environmental justice, among others. Use of such terms may be
379 an indication that a nexus is actually considered even though the words “climate change”,
380 “biodiversity”, “land use” and “local communities” would not appear in the text. Therefore,
381 when conducting nexus related analysis, new methods are needed to capture hidden nexuses
382 through scrutinizing umbrella terms. Furthermore, umbrella terms relate to discourses taking
383 different stances on nexus elements. For example, bioeconomy and circular economy
384 emphasize economic aspects and environmental sustainability. Resilience links to nexus
385 elements as drivers, and to adaptive capacity of social-ecological systems including local
386 communities. Environmental justice starts from Indigenous and local communities’
387 perspectives; they consider fairness aspects of climate change, biodiversity loss and land use
388 impacts on local communities and the local agency. Therefore, future policy document
389 analyses could focus on the ways by which the documents connect the idea of nexus to key
390 concepts and discourses taking different positions on how the nexus should be thought about
391 and dealt with.

392

393 Our results are based on a large set of assessment reports and policy documents, selected by
394 an international expert group on Arctic issues (the authors) to represent a balanced sample of
395 relevant Arctic documents. As with any literature review, a different selection of documents
396 could have resulted in minor differences in results, e.g. in frequencies presented in Figure 2.
397 That said, our numeric results are not intended to be taken as a quantitative assessment but as
398 an illustrative starting point for more specific investigations. The generic definition of
399 “nexus” (a set of context-specific critical interlinkages between two or more elements) makes
400 it challenging to robustly estimate whether there is “adequate” use and a clear understanding
401 of nexus approach present in the documents analyzed or not. Also, comparable analyses from
402 other regions do not exist. Without a baseline it is hard to evaluate what constitutes an

403 'adequate' level of the nexus approach. When dealing with any element of the Arctic policy
404 nexus, any assessment report or strategy paper becomes stronger, when feedbacks and
405 interactions with other crucial nexus elements are considered. This said, it is easy to
406 understand that certain sectoral strategies (for example the EU Farm to Fork strategy, EC
407 2020b, see S1) and assessments with rather narrow scope (for example Bruns 2016 and
408 ACAP 2021, see Note S1) leave these complex interactions out of consideration and state that
409 these are outside the scope of the work.

410

411 **Conclusions**

412

413 Our study provides detailed new knowledge of whether and to what extent Arctic policy
414 documents and assessment reports recognize the Arctic policy nexus: the combination of
415 climate change, biodiversity change, land use and local communities. Furthermore, we
416 examined how challenges related to nexus elements were imagined to be tackled together,
417 through analysis of policy recommendations and knowledge gaps identified in policy
418 documents.

419

420 Our work revealed some aspects of the existence or void of policy coherence in Arctic policy
421 documents and assessment reports, but also identified proposals on how this policy coherence
422 could be strengthened. This increases our understanding of how Arctic challenges can be
423 approached by integrating various policy sectors, like related to energy production and
424 climate change adaptation.

425

426 The potentially significant role of local Arctic communities and traditional livelihoods in
427 environmental governance and societal adaptation is rarely recognized at some governance

428 levels. Inclusion of local communities in the Arctic governance may be incomplete at those
429 governance levels because local livelihoods and their extensive land uses are seen only as
430 something impacted, not as something with agency, impact, and related responsibility. The
431 methodology used in the present paper can be applied for example when studying the
432 temporal development of the nexus consideration in certain types of documents. Further
433 research could also address nexuses of other elements, or examine what specific themes are
434 considered as important in policy documents under the broader categories of climate,
435 biodiversity, and land use, and who are the local communities that receive the most
436 consideration – and who are the ones left behind. Analysis could also be applied beyond the
437 Arctic.

438

439 The present geopolitical situation (Russian war of aggression against Ukraine since February
440 2022 and its cascading effects) has led to unforeseen consequences for Arctic co-operation.
441 Among others, international treaties, cross-border forums in the Barents and Sápmi regions,
442 the role of the EU in the Arctic, and many Indigenous communities are affected. Hence, it is
443 important for future research to investigate whether the Arctic governance regimes, goals and
444 collaborations in the policy documents analyzed are still valid. Are the relatively recent
445 Arctic strategies by the Nordic countries and the EU all suddenly outdated? What will happen
446 to the Arctic Council, in the course of the next years and decades? Scenarios range from
447 “back to the 1990s” optimism to long-term frozen conflict⁶⁷. With so many open questions,
448 we feel that our analysis (which also includes Russian documents) is timely and will open up
449 new viewpoints and ways of analyzing current and future developments in the region. New
450 collaboration structures will emerge at some point, and climate change and biodiversity loss
451 know no borders.

452

453 **Experimental procedures**

454

455 **Resource availability**

456

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459

460 Materials availability

461 This study generated no new materials.

462

463 Data and Code Availability

464 All the literature reviewed in this study is publicly available online or available from authors
465 on request (the literature is listed in Note S1). The data for Figure 2 networks is available in
466 Table S1, analyzed using igraph package⁶⁸ in R environment for statistical computing and
467 graphics⁶⁹.

468

469 **Material selection and document analysis**

470

471 We used document analysis³⁹ combined with qualitative and semi-quantitative content
472 analysis to examine whether policies address nexus elements together⁴⁰. The first step was to
473 select a set of documents relevant for the Arctic policy nexus. The spatial scope considered in
474 this study was a terrestrial subregion of the European Arctic (For a definition of the European

475 Arctic, see <https://climate.copernicus.eu/ESOTC/2019/european-arctic>). This sub-region
476 covers terrestrial regions of Northern Fennoscandian countries (Finland, Norway and
477 Sweden) and European Arctic part of Russia. In this way, we were able to study a continuous
478 area characterized by several land uses and traditional livelihoods and inhabited by
479 Indigenous Peoples, and where various different level policies have an impact.

480

481 We did not carry out a systematic review. The reason for this is that policy documents and
482 material in other languages than English are rarely found in scientific databases. Also, we did
483 not aim at compiling an exhaustive list of all relevant documents, because conducting a
484 qualitative content analysis on a very large volume of text would have been very difficult.
485 Rather, we included a comparable number of documents from each governance level, and in
486 case of national and subnational levels, from each country (Finland, Norway, Sweden, and
487 European Arctic part of Russia) and land-use sector considered. The author group consists of
488 researchers with a long experience of conducting research on climate, biodiversity or land use
489 or working with local communities within the study region, as well as their interlinkages.
490 Researchers fluent in languages spoken in these countries and knowledgeable about land-use
491 issues at these levels suggested documents, and the author group agreed upon the final set of
492 80 documents (Note S1).

493

494 The inclusion or exclusion of a document was determined based on their relevance to the
495 study region and nexus studied, and the year of the publication. As our focus was on present
496 and recent developments, the material we considered spanned the period of approximately ten
497 years, with one document published in 2010 and the rest between 2013 and 2021. Many land-
498 use types exist and livelihoods are practiced within the study region. We selected documents
499 relevant for industrial and traditional types of land use, and emphasized the ones that are,

500 especially at subnational level, considered as significant for local and Indigenous
501 communities and traditional livelihoods. We were also interested in including documents by
502 different actors (like scientific networks, governments, Indigenous actors), with differing
503 agendas. At certain governance levels (for example EU) and from certain publishers (for
504 example the Arctic Council), abundant material regarding our research questions and study
505 region was available. Because we wanted to keep the number of documents balanced between
506 the levels and actors, there was some subjectivity in making the selection, and our aim was to
507 include a broad range of topics covered by the documents. There is some subjectivity in the
508 method, but the expertise in the author group allowed us to select a representative range, and
509 a manageable number, of publicly available assessment reports and policy documents,
510 relevant to our study region, across international, European Union, regional, national, and
511 subnational governance levels.

512

513 The second step was to analyze the documents to identify in each the nexus approach – the
514 acknowledgement of the interactive nature between each pair of nexus elements (Arctic
515 climate, biodiversity, land use, local communities). Specifically, local communities with
516 livelihoods or lifestyles that depend on local ecosystems were emphasized. The selected
517 documents were published in several languages (English, Finnish, Swedish, Norwegian,
518 Russian) and were read by fluent, mainly native, speakers associated to the author group. Key
519 findings were translated into English for comparative analysis.

520

521 The question that was answered per each document, and for each pair of nexus elements, was
522 “How are these nexus elements considered in relation to each other?” Direct citations and
523 short descriptions were presented in tables, which were then used to conduct further analyses.
524 To visualize the findings, co-occurrence networks were constructed based on the frequency

525 of reports acknowledging the connections between each pair of the nexus elements, also
526 representing the governance levels (see Table S1).

527

528 We also identified the acknowledgement of three to four nexus elements together (“full
529 nexus”). An explicit mention of the word “nexus” was not counted. The regional, national
530 and sub-national level documents considered our study region, but the international level
531 assessment reports had circumpolar Arctic scope, and the perspective of most of the EU-level
532 documents was wider than that of the Arctic. Material relevant for our study region was
533 emphasized when analysing these documents.

534

535 We consider policy documents as plans for action. To capture the normative proposals for
536 future policy implementation, the third step was to identify a set of policy recommendations
537 made and knowledge gaps outlined that we interpreted as representing the nexus approach in
538 the documents analyzed. We clustered the policy recommendations and knowledge gaps
539 using qualitative content analysis, and identified key proposals on how policies could better
540 address the nexus elements in an integrated way in the future. We call this “imagined nexus”
541 as both policy recommendations and knowledge gaps are future oriented and contribute to
542 imagining desirable futures. Imaginaries provide grounds for transforming SES through
543 policy innovations by offering accounts of what kinds of futures are possible and
544 desirable^{37,70}. Finally, we discuss the “hidden nexus”, as implied by umbrella terms used in
545 the documents that cover the interlinkages between the nexus elements without mentioning
546 them explicitly. Umbrella terms are integrative concepts; they are part of specific discourses,
547 and their use and acceptance by policy actors shape policies and practices in reality^{65,66}.

548

549

550 **Questions guiding the analysis**

551

552 The material was analyzed by answering the following nine questions per document. Detailed
553 qualitative analysis on links between the nexus elements is found in the CHARTER project
554 deliverable 6.1 (“Biodiversity and land use narrative synthesis based on an extensive
555 literature review”) available here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/869471/results>.

556

557 1.1. How are climate (change/mitigation/impacts/feedbacks) and biodiversity
558 (change/conservation/impacts/feedbacks) considered in relation to each other?

559 1.2. How are climate (change/mitigation/impacts/feedbacks) and land-use
560 (change/governance/impacts/feedbacks) considered in relation to each other?

561 1.3. How are climate (change/mitigation/impacts/feedbacks) and local communities
562 (needs/agency/adaptation/supporting policies/participation/local knowledge, co-management)
563 considered in relation to each other?

564 1.4. How are biodiversity (change/conservation/impacts/feedbacks) and land-use
565 (change/governance/impacts/feedbacks) considered in relation to each other?

566 1.5. How are biodiversity (change/conservation/impacts/feedbacks) and local communities
567 (needs/agency/adaptation/supporting policies/participation/local knowledge, co-management)
568 considered in relation to each other?

569 1.6. How are land-use (change/governance/impacts/feedbacks) and local communities
570 (needs/agency/adaptation/supporting policies/participation/local knowledge, co-management)
571 considered in relation to each other?

572 1.7. How is the “full nexus” considered (three to four aspects together)?

573 2. How are the linkages (climate – land-use – biodiversity – local communities) shown in the
574 policy recommendations given?

575 3. What are the knowledge gaps and research needs mentioned?

576

577 **Co-occurrence networks**

578

579 The co-occurrence networks were constructed for the four governance scales to illustrate
580 potential interlinkages between the four nexus elements (biodiversity, land use, climate
581 change, local communities) in the analyzed reports. First, the material was investigated to
582 capture the paired presence (co-occurrence) of nexus elements: in practice, any two nexus
583 elements were considered to co-occur if they appeared in the text together *and* the text
584 indicated that one element influenced the other in the Arctic. For example, co-occurrence was
585 recorded if a text discussed the impacts of climate change on biodiversity, but not if the text
586 only acknowledged that both climate and biodiversity are changing. This criterion was set to
587 acknowledge the definition of “nexus” as a context-specific, critical interlinkage between two
588 (or more) elements³¹, and to measure how often each nexus element was considered a driver.

589

590 The networks were then generated by using the number of reports in which the different
591 nexus elements co-occurred as network link weights (i.e. strength of the interlinkage,
592 illustrated by link width in Figure 2), presented in Table S1. Thus, the network links visualize
593 the frequency of reports that discuss each co-occurrence, not the frequency of co-occurrences
594 within the reports. Further, the sizes of network nodes illustrate the frequency of reports in
595 which each nexus element was presented as a driver to the other element. To enable
596 comparisons between the four networks, the link weights and node sizes were standardized to
597 0-1 by dividing their values by the number of reports for each regional scale. Since the
598 networks are for visualization only, the width of each link illustrates the total weight of the
599 links between each pair of nexus elements.

600

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610

611 **Author contributions**

612

613 SR, JTE, BCF, ML and MT conceived the study idea with input from all authors. JY, SR and
614 JTE designed the document analysis with input from all authors. ML, MT, MA, NS, DE, TH,
615 SR, JY, JTE, SK, LL, TKo, JOH, CR collected the data (reviewed the material). SR and JY
616 designed the co-occurrence network analysis and JY constructed the networks. SSa and NS
617 made the policy recommendation and knowledge gap analysis. All authors contributed to the
618 writing of the early and final versions of the manuscript. All authors have approved the
619 manuscript for publication. First five authors (SR, JY, SSa, ML and MT) form the core
620 author team; BCF and JTE share the last authorship as senior authors responsible for the
621 coordination of research in addition to roles mentioned above; all other authors besides the
622 first five and last two are listed in alphabetical order.

623

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625

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Figure 1. Research material, nexus approach, and analytical focus used in this study. Graphic by Irina Wang.

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Figure 2. Network visualizations for the co-occurrence of nexus elements in the material analyzed. The widths of the connection between climate change (CC), biodiversity (BD), land use (LU) and local communities (LC) illustrate the ratio of reports analyzed acknowledging each interlinkage. The value next to the connection indicates the ratio of reports that acknowledged the link and is located next to the source (driver) of that connection, standardized by the number of reports analyzed for that governance scale. Zero indicates no outgoing connection. The node sizes illustrate the total frequency of reports that identify each nexus element as a driver. See Note S1 and Table S1 for further details.

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Tables, table titles and captions

Table 1: Examples of policy or action recommendations implying a nexus approach suggested in the documents. Governance levels considered separately. Stakeholders identified for policy or action recommendations are listed either as “Who implements” (responsible bodies; decision-makers, contributors, actors that impose effects) or as “Who are impacted” (target groups; beneficiaries, actors upon which effects are imposed). If no clear distinction was found in the documents, cells are merged. Numbering and full references: see Note S1 and Table S2.

Level	Arctic policy recommendations implying a nexus approach	Who implements?	Who are impacted?
Inter-national/ Arctic	^{110, 113} Protection, conservation and restoration of degraded high-carbon ecosystems such as peatlands, wetlands, rangelands/pastures, and forests; afforestation, reforestation, agroforestry.	Conservation agencies, environmental protection agencies, government	
	^{13, 110} Using a holistic approach and multi-stressor framework to ensure all sectors and downstream effects are considered.	Research institutions, government, environmental protection agencies, industries	
	^{19, 110, 113, 115} Multi-knowledge and multi-disciplinary approaches through meaningful partnership across a range of actors to support adaptive and holistic wetland management.	Businesses, producers, consumers, land managers and government/policymakers	Indigenous Peoples and/or local communities
	^{111, 113} Transformative changes across economic, social, political and technological factors.	Government, policymakers, industries	
	¹¹³ Response options throughout the food system, from production to consumption, including food loss and waste.	Food industry, waste treatment enterprises	
	¹¹³ Adopting sustainable land management practices and improving access to resources and agricultural advisory services.	Government, local communities	
	^{14, 19} Developing standardized climate-ecosystem monitoring, documentation and data collection of the impacts of extreme events, powered by collaboration with Indigenous communities and their local knowledge.	Indigenous communities, scientists	
	¹¹³ Land-use planning and management related to bioenergy.	Government, regional planning agencies, energy companies	

EU	E5, E9 Setting conservation targets in a spatially coherent manner across national scales, matching conservation needs.	Conservation agencies	
	E9, E10 Tailoring policies to address regional and local conditions and needs.	Government (especially at local levels)	Local communities
	E9 Implementing a combination of 'grey' (i.e. technological and engineering solutions), 'green' (i.e. ecosystem-based approaches) and 'soft' (i.e. managerial, legal, policy and market-based approaches) adaptation options.	Government/policymakers, research and innovation institutions, conservation agencies	
	E9 Multi-level governance that bridges the gaps between the different levels of policy and decision-making.	Government (at all levels), local communities	
	E9, E10 Transformational adaptation that involves managing more radical change, rather than restoring a certain environmental or social state and sticking with traditional policy responses.	EU, government, industries, society, citizens (all sectors)	
	E10 Better integration of environment and climate related concerns into sectoral policies, improved implementation.	European Commission, relevant EU agencies, national government, local governments	
	E8 Further work to keep engaging with local and Indigenous Peoples, who possess knowledge of Arctic ecosystems.	EU, Indigenous Peoples, research institutions	
	E12 Tackling the barriers that prevent a massive roll-out and scaling up of renewable energy.	EU, energy companies	
	E6, E10 More effective implementation of and funding for environmental policies to boost sustainable practices, such as precision agriculture, agroecology, carbon farming and agroforestry.	European Commission, Member States, government	
	E10 Cross-sectoral policymaking; holistic, coherent policies that take into consideration different sectors and facilitate coordination.	Government, different sectors and industries	
	E10 Flood protection and drought management.	Relevant government agencies	Local communities, agricultural sectors
	E5 Promoting both economic gains and environmental wellbeing.	Government/policymakers	
E5 Protecting soil health, soil fertility, reducing soil erosion and increasing soil organic matter; identifying contaminated soil sites, restoring degraded soils,	Conservation agencies, environmental protection agencies, scientists		

	monitoring soil quality.		
	E ¹² Developing circular energy, biofuel, and biogas.	Government, energy companies, local communities	
	E ⁶ Transforming the production methods, making the best use of nature-based, technological, digital, and space-based solutions to deliver climate and environmental results.	Farmers, fishers, aquaculture producers, technological innovation companies/agencies	
Regional: Nordic/ Barents/ Sápmi	R ¹ Recognizing the sustainability goals and Indigenous peoples' understanding of society-nature relationships.	Government, regional policymakers	Indigenous Peoples
	R ⁹ Protection and improving the state of reindeer pastures impacted by industrial development.	Industries	Reindeer herders
	R ⁶ Enhancing climate resilience and protecting biodiversity.	Government	Local communities
National	N ³ Promoting low-emission, sustainable, and climate-wise solutions.	Government/policymakers	
	N ³ , N ¹² , N ¹⁶ , N ²⁸ Promoting Arctic food security by safeguarding the preconditions for local industries and traditional livelihoods, protecting Indigenous rights, respecting traditional knowledge.	Government, regional planning agencies, industries	Indigenous Peoples
	N ³ , N ¹⁰ , N ¹⁵ , N ¹⁶ , N ²⁷ Protecting Arctic species and habitats, strengthening the restoration of degraded ecosystems, forestation, implementing stronger and climate-resilient conservation measures.	Government, conservation agencies	
	N ³ Cross-border collaboration related to transboundary watercourses with Sweden, Norway and Russia.	Different national governments	
	N ³ Investing in climate-wise infrastructure and promoting circular economy and bioeconomy to bring new opportunities for employment and livelihoods.	Government, investors	Environmental-friendly industries and companies
	N ¹⁵ Rapid cuts in emissions to protect species and ecosystems.	Industries, government	
	N ⁸ Comprehensive planning of fell habitats and reindeer pastures in the face of growing tourism, and the increasing exploitation of natural resources.	Tourism sector, policymakers, regional planning agencies	Reindeer herders

	N ⁶ Continuing the time series on species monitoring.	Scientists; certain local communities who also conduct monitoring	
	N ¹⁰ Developing new and sustainable solutions in the forest industry, e.g, how to utilize forests in the face of climate change.	Forestry agencies, environmental protection agencies, government, research institutions	
	N ¹² , N ²³ Removal of subsidies, monetary valuation of ecosystem services, limiting habitat loss due to industrial development, substituting fossil energy with bioenergy and biofuels.	Government	Corporations, oil and gas companies
	N ²⁴ Minimizing the burning of side production gas in the petroleum extraction.	Oil and gas companies	People and environment in general
	N ²⁵ Requirements for companies to make climate risk visible in their development plans.	Government	Companies or different land-use sectors in general
Sub-national	S ³ Indigenous participation when planning climate actions.	Indigenous communities, decision-makers, government	
	S ⁶ , S ⁸ , S ¹⁰ , S ¹¹ Sustainable management of the mountains: regulation and enforcement of the regulations for hunting and reindeer herding, establishing of protected areas, enforcement of protection measures.	Indigenous land users and organizations, conservation agencies, government	
	S ⁶ Involving locals in monitoring the treeline change, better modelling to predict this.	Scientists, monitoring stations, local communities	
	S ⁸ , S ¹⁰ Providing local people with increased information on protected species and imposing stricter control over poaching.	Government, conservation agencies	Local peoples

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909 **Table 2.** Examples of knowledge gaps listed in the documents, governance levels considered
910 separately. Stakeholders involved are also listed, either as “Who implements” (responsible
911 bodies; decision-makers, contributors, actors that impose effects) or as “Who are impacted”
912 (target groups; beneficiaries, actors upon which effects are imposed). If no clear distinction
913 was found in the documents, cells are merged. Numbering and full references: See Note S1
914 and Table S3.
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Level	Knowledge Gaps	Who implements?	Who are impacted?
Inter-national / Arctic	^{I10} Mapping Arctic wetlands; developing the existing wetland classification systems; also acknowledging indigenous knowledge of wetlands and wetland use.	Government (e.g. environmental protection agencies), Indigenous communities, research institutions and scientists	
	^{I11} Developing inventories of under-studied ecosystems	Government, research institutions	
	^{I2, I4, I12} Improving understanding and more comprehensive data and projections of precipitation in the polar region, wetting/drying, greening/browning of the Arctic land surface, carbon dioxide and methane emissions from the permafrost, and how changes in these areas affect people environmentally and socio-economically (e.g. Indigenous communities and their food security).	Research institutions, environmental protection agencies, data collection agencies, Indigenous Peoples	
EU	^{E3; E9} Better monitoring of past trends of climate change and their economic, social, and environmental impacts	Research institutions, data and monitoring stations, government	
	^{E10} Monitoring the climate-water-ecosystem-agriculture nexus.	Government, research institutions	
Regional: Nordic/ Barents/ Sápmi	^{R8} Adaptation strategies on how to face new environmental conditions and shifts in biodiversity and how to match political measures and decision-making to changed realities.	Government, research institutions	
	^{R1} Nesting local and regional narratives within global scenario perspectives, to increase the possibility for comparing prospects for mitigation, impact, adaptation, and vulnerabilities across different municipalities, regions and sectors.	Indigenous communities, Indigenous associations, non-governmental organizations, government	
	^{R8} Baseline data on Sámi society, culture, livelihoods.	Researchers, Sámi communities	
	^{R8} Research on Indigenous peoples’ rights connected to land and territories.	Lawyers, researchers, government	Indigenous Peoples
National	^{N5} Exchanges of knowledge between researchers and Indigenous peoples in the Arctic.	Researchers, Indigenous Peoples	

	N6, N8, N9, N27 Development of monitoring of habitats, ecosystems and their functions and changes (e.g. reindeer pastures), and rare species.	Researchers, monitoring stations, Indigenous Peoples
	N25 Further technological developments and research on renewable energy solutions separately and taken together.	Government, energy companies, research and innovation institutions
	N9 Strengthening the communication between the reindeer herding communities, food safety authorities and veterinary research to ensure better monitoring of diseases.	Reindeer herding communities, food safety agencies, research institutes
Sub-national	S7 Better consideration of Traditional Knowledge (árbediehtu); intergenerational transmission of traditional knowledge and Sámi language to secure viable Sámi livelihoods & culture.	Sámi communities, government
	S9, S10, S11 Knowledge of the distribution, the ecology and the threats faced by many rare species of insects, plants and lichens.	Scientists (especially ecologists)
	S14 Research-based knowledge needed in livelihoods like fish farming and reindeer herding.	Scientists, local/Indigenous peoples (e.g. fish farmers, reindeer herders, etc.)

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943 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

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945 **Note S1. Material listing – Assessment reports, policy documents, and**
946 **industrial/sectoral strategies used in the analyses**

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948 **International/Arctic level (15 documents)**

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- 1002 **EU level (13 documents)**
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1280 **Table S1.** Matrices used for co-occurrence networks, showing the frequency of reports in
 1281 which the co-occurrences of each pair of nexus elements were detected. The rows present
 1282 nexus elements as drivers and the columns as targets.

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Table S1 a. Co-occurrence matrix for international scale. In total 15 international reports were analyzed.

	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Local community
Biodiversity		11	10	10
Climate change	2		2	4
Land use	1	7		4
Local community	6	12	8	

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Table S1 b. Co-occurrence matrix for EU scale. In total 13 EU reports were analyzed.

	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Local community
Biodiversity		8	10	2
Climate change	3		10	2
Land use	2	7		0
Local community	2	7	4	

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Table S1 c. Co-occurrence matrix for regional scale. In total 9 regional reports were analyzed.

	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Local community
Biodiversity		3	4	4
Climate change	0		1	4
Land use	3	3		6
Local community	3	6	6	

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Table S1 d. Co-occurrence matrix for national scale. In total 28 national reports were analyzed.

	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Local community
Biodiversity		15	23	9
Climate change	2		13	7
Land use	2	5		11
Local community	4	8	14	

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Table S1 e. Co-occurrence matrix for subnational scale. In total 15 subnational reports were analyzed.

	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Local community
Biodiversity		6	14	13
Climate change	1		4	2
Land use	5	3		9
Local community	4	6	8	

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1304 **Table S2.** Examples of policy or action recommendations implying a nexus approach
1305 suggested in the documents. Governance levels considered separately. Stakeholders identified
1306 for policy or action recommendations are listed either as “Who implements” (responsible
1307 bodies; decision-makers, contributors, actors that impose effects) or as “Who are impacted”
1308 (target groups; beneficiaries, actors upon which effects are imposed). If no clear distinction
1309 was found in the documents, cells are merged.
1310

Level	Arctic Policy Nexus - Policy recommendations	Who implements?	Who are impacted?	Relevant documents
Inter-national/ Arctic	Protection, conservation and restoration of degraded high-carbon ecosystems such as peatlands, wetlands, rangelands/pastures, and forests; afforestation, reforestation, agroforestry.	Conservation agencies, environmental protection agencies, government		CAFF 2021b (I10); Shukla et al. 2019 (I13)
	Using a holistic approach and multi-stressor framework to ensure all sectors and downstream effects are considered.	Research institutions, government, environmental protection agencies, industries		CAFF 2021b (I10); AMAP 2018 (I3)
	Multi-knowledge and multi-disciplinary approaches through meaningful partnership across a range of actors to support adaptive and holistic wetland management.	Businesses, producers, consumers, land managers and government/policymakers	Indigenous Peoples and/or local communities	CAFF 2021a (I9); CAFF 2021b (I10); Shukla et al. 2019 (I13); SDWG 2021 (I15)
	Transformative changes across economic, social, political and technological factors.	Government, policymakers, industries		IPBES 2019 (I11); Shukla et al. 2019 (I13)
	Response options throughout the food system, from production to consumption, including food loss and waste	Food industry, waste treatment enterprises		Shukla et al. 2019 (I13)
	Adopting sustainable land management practices and improving access to resources and agricultural advisory services	Government, local communities		Shukla et al. 2019 (I13)
	Developing standardized climate-ecosystem monitoring, documentation and data collection of the impacts of extreme events, powered by collaboration with Indigenous communities and their local knowledge	Indigenous communities, scientists		AMAP 2021 (I4); CAFF 2021a (I9);
	Land-use planning and management related to bioenergy	Government, regional planning agencies, energy companies		Shukla et al. 2019 (I13)
EU	Setting conservation targets in a spatially coherent manner across national scales, matching conservation needs	Conservation agencies		EEA 2017 (E9); EC 2021b (E5)

Tailoring policies to address regional and local conditions and needs	Government (especially on local levels)	Local communities	EEA 2017 (E9); EEA 2020 (E10)
Implementing a combination of 'grey' (i.e. technological and engineering solutions), 'green' (i.e. ecosystem-based approaches) and 'soft' (i.e. managerial, legal, policy and market-based approaches) adaptation options.	Government/policymakers, research and innovation institutions, conservation agencies		EEA 2017 (E9)
Multi-level governance that bridges the gaps between the different levels of policy and decision-making.	Government (at all levels), local communities		EEA 2017 (E9)
Transformational adaptation that involves managing more radical change, rather than restoring a certain environmental or social state and sticking with traditional policy responses	EU, government, industries, society, citizens (all sectors)		EEA 2017 (E9); EEA 2020 (E10)
Better integration of environment and climate related concerns into sectoral policies, improved implementation.	European Commission, relevant EU agencies, national government, local governments		EEA 2020 (E10)
Further work to keep engaging with local and Indigenous Peoples, who possess knowledge of Arctic ecosystems	EU, Indigenous Peoples, research institutions		EC 2021c (E8)
Tackling the barriers that prevent a massive roll-out and scaling up of renewable energy	EU, energy companies		EC 2021c (E12)
More effective implementation of and funding for environmental policies to boost sustainable practices, such as precision agriculture, agro-ecology, carbon farming and agroforestry	European Commission, Member States, government		EEA 2020 (E10); EC 2020b (E6)
Cross-sectoral policymaking; holistic, coherent policies that take into consideration different sectors and facilitate coordination	Government, different sectors and industries		EEA 2020 (E10)
Flood protection and drought management	Relevant government agencies	Local communities, agricultural sectors	EEA 2020 (E10)
Promoting both economic gains and environmental wellbeing.	Government/policymakers		EC 2021b (E5)
Protecting soil health, soil fertility, reducing soil erosion and increasing soil organic matter; identifying contaminated	Conservation agencies, environmental protection agencies, scientists		EC 2021b (E5)

	soil sites, restoring degraded soils, monitoring soil quality			
	Developing circular energy, biofuel, and biogas.	Government, energy companies, local communities		EC 2020c (E12)
	Transforming the production methods, making the best use of nature-based, technological, digital, and space-based solutions to deliver climate and environmental results.	Farmers, fishers, aquaculture producers, technological innovation companies/agencies		EC 2020b (E6)
Nordic/ Barents/ Sápmi	Recognizing the sustainability goals and Indigenous peoples' understanding of society-nature relationships.	Government, regional policymakers	Indigenous Peoples	AMAP 2017 (R1)
	Protection and improving the state of reindeer pastures impacted by industrial development.	Industries	Reindeer herders	WRHC 2017 (R9)
	Enhancing climate resilience and protecting biodiversity.	Government	Local communities	Nordregio secretariat 2021a (R6)
National	Promoting low-emission, sustainable, and climate-wise solutions	Government/policymakers		Finnish Government 2021 (N3)
	Promoting Arctic food security by safeguarding the preconditions for local industries and traditional livelihoods, protecting Indigenous rights, respecting traditional knowledge.	Government, regional planning agencies, industries	Indigenous Peoples	Finnish Government 2021 (N3); Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation 2015 (N12); President of Russia 2020 (N16); Government of the Russian Federation 2013 (N28)
	Protecting Arctic species and habitats, strengthening the restoration of degraded ecosystems, forestation, implementing stronger and climate-resilient conservation measures	Government, conservation agencies		Finnish Government 2021 (N3); Norwegian Ministries 2021 (N15); President of Russia 2020 (N16); Government of the Russian Federation 2014 (N27); Ministry of Agriculture and Food of Norway 2016 (N10)
	Cross-border collaboration related to transboundary water courses with Sweden, Norway and Russia	Different national governments		Finnish Government 2021 (N3)

	Investing in climate-wise infrastructure and promoting circular economy and bioeconomy to bring new opportunities for employment and livelihoods	Government, investors	Environmental-friendly industries and companies	Finnish Government 2021 (N3)
	Rapid cuts in emissions to protect species and ecosystems	Industries, government		Norwegian Ministries 2021 (N15)
	Comprehensive planning of fell habitats and reindeer pastures in the face of growing tourism, and the increasing exploitation of natural resources	Tourism sector, policymakers, regional planning agencies	Reindeer herders	Kontula & Raunio 2019 (N8)
	Continuing the time series on species monitoring	Scientists; certain local communities who also conduct monitoring		Jakobsson & Pedersen 2020 (N6)
	Developing new and sustainable solutions in the forest industry, e.g, how to utilize forests in the face of climate change	Forestry agencies, environmental protection agencies, government, research institutions		Ministry of Agriculture and Food of Norway 2016 (N10)
	Removal of subsidies, monetary valuation of ecosystem services, limiting habitat loss due to industrial development, substituting fossil energy with bioenergy and biofuels	Government	Corporations, oil and gas companies	Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation 2015 (N12); Bioenergia ry 2020 (N23)
	Minimizing the burning of side production gas in the petroleum extraction	Oil and gas companies	People and environment in general	Government of the Russian Federation 2020 (N4)
	Requirements for companies to make climate risk visible in their development plans	Government	Companies or different land-use sectors in general	Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of Norway 2020 (N25)
Sub-national	Indigenous participation when planning climate actions	Indigenous communities, decision-makers, government		Lapin liitto 2021 (S3)
	Sustainable management of the mountains: regulation and enforcement of the regulations for hunting and reindeer herding, creation of protected areas, enforcement of protection measures	Indigenous and local land users and organizations, conservation agencies, government		The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency 2019 (S6); Ektova & Zamyatin 2010 (S11); Degteva & Polshvedkin 2019 (S10); Shweizer et al. 2014 (S8)
	Involving locals in monitoring the treeline change, better modelling to predict this.	Scientists, monitoring stations, local communities		The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency 2019 (S6)

	Providing local people with increased information about protected species and implementing stronger control of poaching	Government, conservation agencies	Local peoples	Degteva & Polshvedkin 2019 (S10); Shweizer et al. 2014 (S8)
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Table S3. Examples of knowledge gaps listed in the documents, governance levels considered separately. Stakeholders involved are also listed, either as “Who implements” (responsible bodies; decision-makers, contributors, actors that impose effects) or as “Who are impacted” (target groups; beneficiaries, actors upon which effects are imposed). If no clear distinction was found in the documents, cells are merged.

Level	Knowledge Gaps	Who implements?	Who are impacted?	Relevant documents
Inter-national / Arctic	Mapping Arctic wetlands; developing the existing wetland classification systems; also acknowledging indigenous knowledge on wetlands and wetland use.	Government (e.g. environmental protection agencies), Indigenous communities, research institutions and scientists		CAFF 2021b (I10)
	Developing inventories on under-studied ecosystems	Government, research institutions		IPBES 2019 (I11)
	Improving understanding and more comprehensive data and projections of precipitation in the polar region, wetting/drying, greening/browning of the Arctic land surface, carbon dioxide and methane emissions from the permafrost, and how changes in these areas affect people environmentally and socio-economically (e.g. Indigenous communities and their food security)	Research institutions, environmental protection agencies, data collection agencies, Indigenous Peoples		Meredith et al. 2019 (I12); AMAP 2017 (I2); AMAP 2021 (I4)
EU	Better monitoring of past trends of climate change and their economic, social, and environmental impacts	Research institutions, data and monitoring stations, government		EC 2017 (E3); EEA 2017 (E9)
	Monitoring the climate-water-ecosystem-agriculture nexus.	Government, research institutions		EEA 2020 (E10)
Nordic/ Barents/ Sápmi	Adaptation strategies on how to face new environmental conditions and shifts in biodiversity and how to match political measures and decision-making to changed realities	Government, research institutions		The Saami Council 2019 (R8)
	Nesting local and regional narratives within global scenario perspectives, to increase the possibility for comparing prospects for mitigation, impact, adaptation, and	Indigenous communities, Indigenous associations, NGOs, government		AMAP 2017 (R1)

	vulnerabilities across different municipalities, regions and sectors.		
	Baseline data on the Sámi people, society, culture, livelihoods.	Researchers, Sámi communities	The Saami Council 2019 (R8)
	Research on Indigenous peoples' rights connected to land and territories.	Lawyers, researchers, government	Indigenous Peoples The Saami Council 2019 (R8)
National	Exchanges of knowledge between researchers and Indigenous peoples in the Arctic	Researchers, Indigenous Peoples	Government Offices of Sweden 2020 (N5)
	Development of monitoring of habitats, ecosystems and their functions and changes (e.g. reindeer pastures), and rare species.	Researchers, monitoring stations, Indigenous Peoples	Kontula & Raunio 2019 (N8); Jakobsson & Pedersen 2020 (N6); Government of the Russian Federation 2014 (N27); Ministry of Agriculture and Food of Norway 2016 (N9)
	Further technological developments and research on renewable energy solutions separately and seen together.	Government, energy companies, research and innovation institutions	Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of Norway 2020 (N25)
	Strengthening the communication between the reindeer herding communities, food safety authorities and veterinary research to ensure better monitoring of diseases	Reindeer herding communities, food safety agencies, research institutes	Ministry of Agriculture and Food of Norway 2016 (N9)
Sub-national	Better consideration of Traditional knowledge (árbediehtu); intergenerational transmission of traditional knowledge and Sámi language to secure healthy Sámi livelihoods & culture.	Sámi communities, government	The Swedish Sami Parliament 2021 (S7)
	Knowledge about the distribution, the ecology and the threats for many rare species of insects, plants and lichens	Scientists (especially ecologists)	Matveeva 2020 (S9); Degteva & Polshvedkin 2019 (S10); Ektova & Zamyatin 2010 (S11)
	Research-based knowledge needed in livelihoods like fish farming and reindeer herding.	Scientists, local/Indigenous peoples (e.g. fish farmers, reindeer herders, etc.)	Deputy Assembly of the Nenets Autonomous Okrug 2019 (S14)

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